

A MULTI-SCALE GEANT4-BASED SIMULATION PLATFORM FOR THE PREDICTION OF EARLY BIOLOGICAL DAMAGE DURING SPACE MISSIONS. A. Paillet¹, J. W. Choi², M. Asai³, A. Le Postollec⁴, M. Dobrijevic⁴, H. N. Tran¹, Y. S. Yeom², S. Incerti¹, ¹Université de Bordeaux, CNRS, LP2I, UMR 5797, F-33170 Gradignan, France, ²Radiation Convergence Engineering, Yonsei University, Wonju, South Korea, ³Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility, 12000 Jefferson Avenue, Newport News, VA, USA, ⁴Univ. Bordeaux, CNRS, LAB, UMR 5804, F-33600 Pessac, France.

Introduction: Being able to simulate, at the cellular scale, the mechanistic effects of ionizing radiation-induced biological damage during manned space exploration missions remains a technical challenge. We introduce a multi-scale simulation platform based on the Geant4 general-purpose Monte Carlo simulation toolkit [1-4] to simulate early DNA damage induction in cells from physical interactions and radiolysis. The feasibility of such an approach has recently been demonstrated [5]. In this work, we propose to simulate early biological damage induced in cosmonauts' cells in the context of the ARTEMIS II mission.

Materials and methods:

The platform is based on a combination of three existing examples provided with the Geant4 toolkit that deal with three different geometry scales. The first is the *gorad* example [6], used to simulate the radiation environment surrounding the realistic spacecraft geometry (meter scale). The second application is the *ICRP145_HumanPhantoms* example [7], which enables irradiation of realistic tessellated male and female human phantoms across various irradiation fields (cm scale). Finally, the third example is the *moleculardna* example [8], which can simulate the induction of early biological damage at the single-cell level (sub-micrometer scale). We seamlessly combine these examples with interconnecting phase-space files that contain all necessary information for simulating ionizing particles across three different scales.

Data and code: All data and codes used are open-source. Moreover, a coherent set of scripts will be made available to the community to simplify platform use. For example, by providing a GCR spectrum as an input parameter, we aim to provide a quantitative estimate of DNA damage in a few organs of interest (brain, eyes, spleen, pancreas, etc.).

Preliminary results: As a first step, we calculated the dose delivered to standing male and female phantoms placed at the center of the Orion module using Geant4 version 11.4.0. For a fictive mission duration of one year, considering GCR spectra (protons, alpha particles, C, N, and O ions), the typical absorbed doses in organs are presented.

Conclusion and perspectives: The initial results presented in this study are encouraging. We are currently working to predict early radiation-induced damage at the single-cell level from exposure to GCR and SPE across different organs in human

phantoms, adopting different positions (e.g., seating phantoms). The platform will also be adapted to a lunar habitat [9].

References:

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